

HOLISTIC SOLUTIONS FOR CHRONIC LOW BACK PAIN: INTEGRATING ICF CORE SETS WITH REHABILITATION PROBLEM-SOLVING FORM - STRATEGIC PATHWAYS IN PHYSIOTHERAPY

Dr. Janani Arul

Assistant Professor, College of Physiotherapy, School of Health Sciences, Dayananda Sagar University,
Harohalli, Kanakpura road,
Ramanagara Dt.-562112, Karnataka, India

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14780311

Introduction:

A large number of people globally suffer from the common and disabling condition known as chronic low back pain (CLBP). Many people still struggle with chronic pain and functional impairments even with a wide range of treatment choices available, which lowers their quality of life and raises healthcare expenses. Traditional approaches frequently concentrate on managing symptoms rather than addressing the underlying causes of the recurrence.¹ One of the challenges in managing CLBP is the lack of a holistic, patient-centred approach that integrates both physical support and cognitive-behavioral strategies. Additionally, patients with CLBP frequently face difficulties in problem-solving and managing the daily challenges of their condition, which can further aggravates their symptoms and delay recovery.²

There is a need for a comprehensive rehabilitation plan that not only provides physical support but also encourages patients to actively participate in their recovery. The combination of ICF corsets and a Rehabilitation Problem-Solving Form provides an effective solution to this issue by addressing both the physical and psychological components of CLBP.³

However, the efficacy of this combination approach in improving patient outcomes has not been widely practised by among physiotherapist, hence this study provide an idea for a better strategy for chronic low back pain management. This study aims to fill that gap by examining the effects of ICF core sets and the Rehabilitation Problem-Solving Form on pain relief, functional progress, and overall patient satisfaction in those with chronic low back pain. The results will provide useful insights into the potential benefits of a more holistic and integrated rehabilitation approach, with the goal.

SOLUTION TO THE PROBLEM STATEMENT:

To address the challenges presented by chronic low back pain (CLBP) and the limitations of current treatment approaches, the proposed solution integrates the use of ICF (International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health) core⁴ sets with a Rehabilitation Problem Solving Form as a comprehensive rehabilitation strategy. This dual approach aims to target both the physical and psychological aspects of CLBP, providing a more holistic method for pain management and functional improvement.

- 1. ICF Core sets for Physical Support:** ICF core sets are designed to provide targeted assessment in a brief & comprehensive way which helps to alleviate pain by providing treatment according to needs of physical & functional impairments by applying clinical practice guidelines revised 2021 for the specific physical impairments. By physically supporting the affected area, these core sets can play a crucial role in reducing pain intensity and preventing further injury during daily activities. The use of ICF core sets in this strategy ensures that patients receive the necessary physical aid to manage their condition effectively.^{3,4}

2. **Rehabilitation Problem-Solving Form for Cognitive-Behavioral Support:** The Rehabilitation Problem-Solving Form is a structured tool that guides patients in identifying and addressing the various challenges associated with their CLBP.⁸ This form encourages patients to engage in cognitive-behavioral techniques, such as goal setting, problem analysis, and the development of actionable solutions by applying Bio psychosocial Approaches into Physiotherapy Management. This strategy encourages greater levels of self-efficacy, enhances coping strategies, and makes it easier for patients to manage their conditions over the long term by giving patients the power to take an active role in their rehabilitation.⁵
3. **Integrated Approach for Enhanced Outcomes:** By combining the physical support of ICF corsets with the cognitive-behavioral benefits of the Rehabilitation Problem Solving Form, this solution offers a comprehensive rehabilitation strategy that addresses the multifaceted nature of CLBP.^{6,7} This integrated approach not only aims to reduce pain and improve functional ability but also seeks to enhance the overall quality of life for individuals with chronic low back pain by applying clinical practice guideline for low back pain as an evidence based treatment approach.

UNIQUENESS / INNOVATION:

The proposed approach of integrating ICF corsets with the Rehabilitation Problem Solving Form offers a unique and innovative solution to the complex challenge of chronic low back pain (CLBP). The distinctiveness of this approach lies in its holistic, dual-focused strategy that simultaneously addresses the physical and cognitive-behavioral aspects of the condition, setting it apart from traditional treatment methods.

The core sets which is provided by WHO and rehabilitation problem solving form is available in the market and it is open access which will be great use for the physiotherapist to use for the integrated approach for chronic low back pain patient by applying the treatment by clinical practice guideline for low back pain as an evidence based treatment approach which will improve physical, functional and the quality of life Influencing the physiotherapist about the use of ICF core sets by WHO & rehabilitation problem solving form as a tool and Idea of Innovation in Physiotherapy Management of Low Back Pain for the better outcome of the patient pain management.

I hope and assure that this idea of using ICF core sets & rehabilitation problem solving form helps in managing the low back pain patients and also a new rehabilitation strategy for the physiotherapist to improve the physical and functional quality of the life of the patients by applying the evidence-based practice in the rehabilitation process.

Reference:

1. Yang J, Lo WLA, Zheng F, Cheng X, Yu Q, Wang C. Evaluation of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on Improving Pain, Fear Avoidance, and Self-Efficacy in Patients with Chronic Low Back Pain: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Pain Res Manag.* 2022 Mar 19;2022:4276175. doi: 10.1155/2022/4276175. PMID: 35345623; PMCID: PMC8957446.
2. Almutairi NA, Almarwani MM. Knowledge and use of the International Classification of Functioning, disability and health (ICF) and ICF Core Sets for musculoskeletal conditions among saudi physical therapists. *Musculoskelet Sci Pract.* 2022 Aug;60:102573. doi: 10.1016/j.msksp.2022.102573. Epub 2022 May 1. PMID: 35533598
3. Geyh, S., Peter, C., Müller, R., & Stucki, G. (2011). "Rehabilitation problem-solving: Integrating the ICF in clinical practice." *Rehabilitation Psychology*, 56(3), 244-249.
4. Cieza, A., & Stucki, G. (2004). "ICF Core Sets for Low Back Pain." *Journal of Rehabilitation Medicine*, Supplement 44.
5. Werner A Steiner, Liliane Ryser, Erika Huber, Daniel Uebelhart, André Aeschlimann, Gerold Stucki, Use of the ICF Model as a Clinical Problem-Solving Tool in Physical Therapy and Rehabilitation Medicine, *Physical Therapy*, Volume 82, Issue 11, 1 November 2002, Pages 1098–1107
6. Linton, S. J., et al. (2021). "Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy for Low Back Pain: A Review." *Pain Research and Management*.
7. Stier-Jarmer, M., Cieza, A., Borchers, M., & Stucki, G. (2009). "How to apply the ICF and ICF core sets for low back pain." *Clinical Journal of Pain*.
8. Sean D Rundell, Todd E Davenport, Tracey Wagner, Physical Therapist Management of Acute and Chronic Low Back Pain Using the World Health Organization's International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health, *Physical Therapy*, Volume 89, Issue 1, 1 January 2009, Pages 82–90, <https://doi.org/10.2522/ptj.20080113>